

Towards individualized model-based audiology: Assessing the prediction accuracy and degrees of individualization of the auditory model FADE for hearing-impaired listeners in complex acoustic scenes

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Keywords

Model-based audiology, complex acoustic scenes, speech intelligibility, automatic speech recognition, speech intelligibility prediction

Highlights

- The FADE model is evaluated for standard conditions and complex acoustic scenes.
- Speech recognition is predicted for normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners.
- The model's prediction accuracy and required individualization degree are assessed.
- A benchmark for building blocks required for model-based audiology is constructed.

Abstract

Model-based audiology aims at optimizing diagnostics and individual benefit from hearing devices using auditory models for a quantitative prediction of individual human hearing performance with only few measured parameters. As speech recognition in noise is an essential quantity, models aim at systematically and precisely predicting the hearing performance in various listening conditions. However, current evaluations focus on simple acoustic conditions that differ from realistic listening scenarios, so an evaluation of the prediction accuracy of auditory models in complex acoustic scenes is required.

In this study, speech recognition thresholds (SRTs) of age-matched normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners in standard conditions (SON0) and (SON90) and complex acoustic scenes (living room, pub, underground station) were predicted by the Simulation Framework for Auditory Discrimination Experiments (FADE). For an application in model-based audiology aiming at a precise characterization of individual listeners, a particular focus was set on modeling inter-individual variability by applying three different individualization strategies of increasing complexity, based on the audiogram combined with a generic, pure-tone-average-based, or tone-in-noise-detection-based suprathreshold component.

FADE showed good agreement with empirical SRTs across conditions but consistently predicted lower SRTs. An individualized suprathreshold component was beneficial for the prediction accuracy compared to the generic strategy, and the tone-in-noise based strategy resulted in the highest accuracy of model predictions. By predicting the overall effects of the acoustic conditions and individual speech recognition results, the findings demonstrate the applicability of auditory modeling in acoustically complex scenes and highlight the importance of suprathreshold auditory processing for individualized model-based audiology.

1. Introduction

This article deals with the evaluation of FADE, a model for precise, individualized speech recognition predictions, as a building block on the way towards model-based audiology, i.e., the usage of computational auditory models to quantitatively predict and understand human hearing performance based on basic principles and using as few parameters as possible (Fontan et al., 2020; Kollmeier and Kiessling, 2018; Mahomed-Asmail et al., 2024; Schädler et al., 2018). In combination with only a few essential empirical measurements characterizing an individual patient, the use of auditory models aims at precisely predicting the performance of the individual listener under diverse conditions, ultimately both for unaided cases and cases involving a hearing device. Model-based audiology also provides a systematic approach to advancing our understanding of how hearing impairment affects speech recognition. It may therefore offer an efficient framework to evaluate the effectiveness of different speech recognition test conditions for providing diagnostic data on the individual listener or for predicting the individual benefit with a hearing device, thereby serving as a quality control or a check of fulfilled prerequisites for a successful provision with hearing devices. This requires the availability of appropriate auditory models that provide a high prediction accuracy and the potential for being fitted to an individual listener by a small set of fundamental parameters characterizing the individual hearing loss, e.g., the audiogram, tone-in-noise detection thresholds, and / or speech recognition scores in a selected set of conditions.

In the present study, the prediction accuracy and individualization capability of the auditory model Simulation Framework for Auditory Discrimination Experiments (FADE) (Kollmeier et al., 2016; Schädler et al., 2020b, 2020a, 2016) is evaluated for hearing-impaired listeners across different acoustic conditions. These involve audiological standard conditions and complex acoustic scenes, including reverberation and realistic listening conditions such as speech-on-speech and speech-in-music backgrounds. In addition, the predictive accuracy of FADE is further evaluated under different strategies for individualizing hearing loss, with the goal of identifying strategies that best capture inter-individual variability in speech recognition performance, including suprathreshold deficits.

Importantly, such evaluation of a model's prediction accuracy in acoustically complex scenes is motivated by the fact that in everyday life, hearing aid users are frequently exposed to background noise, spatially distributed sound sources, reverberation, and competing talkers. These conditions contrast with the simplified test conditions typically used in clinical audiology (Patou, 2022; Weisser et al., 2019). To increase ecological validity, it is therefore essential to investigate test conditions that more closely approximate real-world acoustic challenges. For the application of model-based audiology for conditions of relevance in everyday life, an auditory model, like FADE, should be evaluated in terms of its prediction accuracy and capability of individualizing for a certain listener in such conditions. To address complex acoustic scenes, speech recognition models can be combined with room acoustic simulations (Ahrens et al., 2019; Gerken et al., 2025a, 2024; Schütze et al., 2025). This enables a systematic investigation and variation of key factors such as spatial source distributions and the amount of reverberation.

In addition to environmental complexity, a second major challenge in hearing research is the large inter-individual variability observed in hearing-impaired listeners. Such variability has been reported across multiple perceptual domains, including loudness perception (Oetting et al., 2016) and listening effort (Krueger et al., 2017; Wagner et al., 2019), but is particularly pronounced in speech recognition. This applies both to absolute speech recognition performance (Best et al., 2017; Holube et al., 2024; Lavandier et al., 2021; Wagener and Brand, 2005) and to the benefit in speech recognition from hearing aids (Stenfelt, 2008). Notably, substantial differences in speech recognition abilities are often observed even among listeners with similar audiograms, indicating that the audiogram alone is insufficient for accounting for individual performance.

In this context, model-based audiology provides a framework to address both challenges. A wide variety of speech recognition models exists, including approaches based on energetic masking (e.g., Beutelmann et al., 2010), envelope-based representations (e.g., Jørgensen et al., 2013), and automatic speech recognition (ASR) (e.g., Roßbach et al., 2022), each with specific strengths and limitations. An overview of available models is given in Lavandier and Best (2020) and Schädler et al. (2018). For the application in model-based audiology in complex acoustic scenes, models should ideally fulfill several requirements, including: i) allow individualization to different listeners, ii) process binaural signals, iii) operate on mixed signals without requiring separate speech and/or noise inputs, iv) function without empirical reference data, and v) generate aided predictions. Among existing approaches, the ASR-based model FADE (Kollmeier et al., 2016; Schädler et al., 2020b, 2016) meets all these criteria, unlike many other models. This qualifies FADE as an appropriate building block for model-based audiology which justifies that no other model has been included in this study for comparison.

FADE can be assigned to the category of machine learning-based models, acting as a compromise between traditional knowledge-based models and modern end-to-end models based on artificial intelligence by using interpretable processing steps. It has primarily been used in the literature to predict speech recognition thresholds (SRT), i.e., the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) corresponding to 50% speech recognition. Beyond speech recognition, FADE can be used for psychoacoustic simulations, including tone detection thresholds in quiet and in noise, supporting precise listener individualization (Schädler et al., 2020a). A binaural extension applying contralateral inhibition has been introduced by Schädler et al. (2020b) and evaluated in complex acoustic conditions by Gerken et al. (2025a).

FADE has been evaluated for normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners across different listening conditions (quiet, stationary and fluctuating noise) and binaural configurations (Hülsmeyer et al., 2021; Kollmeier et al., 2016; Schädler et al., 2020b, 2016). Previous efforts towards evaluating FADE's prediction accuracy for complex acoustic scenes have focused on normal-hearing listeners in virtual room environments (Gerken et al., 2025a). While this study demonstrated that FADE captures the effects of spatial complexity and realistic sound source arrangements, it was limited to stationary noise, a single room environment, and did not include hearing-impaired listeners, the primary target group in model-based audiology. Thus, the evaluation of FADE's prediction accuracy in complex acoustic scenes for hearing-impaired listeners remains unaddressed, forming the central aim of the present study.

FADE can be individualized to listeners using strategies that differ in the amount of listener-specific information incorporated. The simplest strategy relies on the individual pure-tone hearing threshold, reflecting solely audibility aspects. While this strategy can yield accurate predictions on the group level, particularly for groups with heterogeneous audiograms, it fails to capture inter-individual differences in speech perception (Schädler et al., 2018). To address this limitation, a suprathreshold distortion component (D-component), as originally proposed by Plomp (1978), can be incorporated. In FADE, this component is implemented as multiplicative noise in the feature extraction, simulating the increased level uncertainty or suprathreshold auditory deficits that go beyond audibility (Kollmeier et al., 2016). Depending on the available listener data, different strategies for incorporating the D-component can be applied. A generic D-component can be used when only limited information is available, providing a uniform baseline of suprathreshold distortion across listeners. A more individualized strategy derives the D-component from the pure tone average (PTA) (Hülsmeyer et al., 2022), capturing coarse differences in suprathreshold deficits associated with overall hearing loss. The most detailed individualization strategy utilizes tone-in-noise (TIN) detection thresholds, which directly reflect a listener's ability to detect sound in noise. Unlike the other strategies, the TIN-based individualization generates a frequency-dependent D-component, allowing for a more precise representation of listener-specific suprathreshold processing, although at the cost of increased measurement effort

(Schädler et al., 2020a). Previous work has compared these individualization strategies for monaural SRT predictions in quiet and in stationary and fluctuating noise Hülsmeyer and Kollmeier (2022). While the use of a PTA-based D-component improved prediction accuracy compared to a generic D-component, the highest prediction accuracy was obtained by combining TIN-based individualization in combination with an adaptive, precise sweep audiogram. However, these individualization strategies have not yet been evaluated in complex acoustic scenes involving binaural processing and realistic signals. Addressing this gap, the present study systematically compares generic, PTA-based, and TIN-based individualization strategies using binaural FADE in ecologically valid listening conditions, including reverberation and realistic maskers such as speech and music. This allows the assessment of how the degree of listener-specific modeling affects the accuracy of speech recognition predictions under conditions reflecting real-world challenges.

A dedicated benchmark database is required to evaluate the model accuracy under acoustically complex conditions. However, suitable datasets are scarce, as most are either not publicly available, lack acoustically complex conditions, or include only a limited number of listeners (Gieseler et al., 2017; Jafri et al., 2025; Kameroner et al., 2019; Regev et al., 2025; Rönnberg et al., 2016; Sanchez-Lopez et al., 2021; Vlaming et al., 2011). The dataset used here (Afghah et al., 2025; Gerken et al., 2026) addresses these limitations by providing a comprehensive set of audiological measurements, including SRTs both in conditions typically used in audiology, as well as in virtual complex acoustic scenes, for normal-hearing and hearing-impaired listeners. One goal of the current paper is to upgrade this dataset into a benchmark for building blocks of model-based audiology by supplementing the available empirical data with predictions from FADE as one suitable auditory model, thus enabling other researchers to test and optimize their respective approaches in comparison to FADE.

The study addresses the following research questions: 1) To what extent can FADE predict speech recognition performance in complex acoustic scenes for hearing-impaired listeners? 2) How does the accuracy of speech recognition predictions change with increasing levels of listener-specific individualization?

To address both questions, the present study evaluates FADE using data from hearing-impaired and age-matched normal-hearing listeners, covering a broad range of audiological variability. Model predictions are compared with empirical data from a large database, which includes both standard clinical conditions and complex acoustic scenes. To identify the optimal individualization strategy, FADE is individualized using the listener's pure-tone audiogram in combination with three alternative strategies for incorporating the suprathreshold distortion component (generic, PTA-based, and TIN-based), which are systematically compared in terms of their predictive accuracy.

2. Methods

2.1 Speech recognition measurement database

The present study is based on a comprehensive dataset of hearing-impaired listeners and age-matched normal-hearing controls from the CRC HAPPA database (Afghah et al., 2025; Gerken et al., 2026). This database contains measurements of speech intelligibility, listening effort, loudness scaling, TIN detection thresholds, and the HEAR-COMMAND tool questionnaire (Afghah et al., 2022; Alfakir et al., 2025). Speech intelligibility has been measured in both standard audiological conditions and virtual acoustic scenes. The standard conditions included co-located speech in noise (SON0) and spatially separated speech and noise (SON90). Additionally, measurements were conducted in four complex acoustic scenes: a living room (asymmetric setup), a living room (symmetric setup), a pub, and an underground station. Further details on the measurement procedures and experimental setup are provided in Afghah et al. (2025) and Gerken et al. (2026).

2.1.1 Listeners

The database includes a total of 76 listeners (35 female and 41 male) with a mean age of 74.0 ± 7.1 years (mean \pm standard deviation). Of these listeners, 20 were normal-hearing (aged 71.5 ± 8.8 years, denoted as “NH”), 25 were hearing-impaired without hearing aids (aged 74.1 ± 6.5 years, denoted as “HI without HA”), and 31 were hearing-impaired who used own hearing aids in daily life (aged 75.5 ± 6.0 years, denoted as “HI with HA (unaided)”). Listeners were defined as normal-hearing if the PTA across the frequencies 0.5, 1, 2 and 4 kHz and across ears was below 25 dB HL. Hearing-impaired listeners wearing hearing aids were measured both aided and unaided. However, the current contribution focuses exclusively on unaided measurements. Since the current analysis utilizes TIN detection thresholds for parts of the model predictions, one listener from the NH group was excluded from the analyses due to missing TIN data to ensure comparability across individualization strategies. Consequently, the analyses in the current paper are based on 75 listeners.

2.1.2 Psychoacoustic measurements

Clinical audiograms were measured by experienced staff at Hörzentrum Oldenburg at the frequencies 0.125, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 6, and 8 kHz for both ears. TIN detection thresholds were measured using the Single Interval Adjustment Matrix (SIAM) procedure (Kaernbach, 1990) at the frequencies 0.5 and 2 kHz for each ear separately. In each trial, a single 800 ms long interval was presented, containing a two-octave-wide white noise centered at the respective tone frequency. The broadband noise level (20 Hz to 8 kHz) was fixed at 69 dB SPL. At a 50% chance level, a 200 ms long tone was present within the noise, with an initial level of 60 dB SPL. An adaptive procedure was used to estimate the detection threshold corresponding to 87.5% correct identification of tones (Schädler et al., 2020a). Stimuli were presented via free-field equalized Sennheiser HDA 200 headphones (ISO 389-8, 2004) and an RME Fireface UCX II audio interface with a sampling rate of 44.1 kHz.

2.1.3 Speech intelligibility measurements

Speech intelligibility in terms of the speech recognition threshold (SRT) at 50% was measured in six different conditions using the Oldenburg sentence test (OLSA) (Wagener et al., 1999). Measurements were conducted in an acoustically treated free-field laboratory at Hörzentrum Oldenburg using a 24-channel horizontal loudspeaker array.

Two standard conditions well-established in audiological practice included co-located speech and masker from the front (SON0), and a spatially separated condition with speech from the front and the masker from 90° azimuth (SON90). The test-specific, stationary masker (Olnoise) was presented at a fixed level of 65 dB SPL. Additionally, four complex conditions in virtual acoustic scenes (van de Par et al., 2022) were measured. This included an asymmetric setting in a living room (label “Living room (asym)”), a symmetric setting in a living room (label “Living room (sym)”), a pub (label “Pub”), and an underground station (label “Underground”). These scenes were designed to reflect realistic listening scenarios with spatially distributed speech and masker sources, reverberation, and realistic masker signals. A more detailed overview of the acoustic conditions and their implementation is provided in Gerken et al. (2026).

2.2 Speech recognition performance predictions with FADE

The aim of the current study was to evaluate the FADE model (Schädler et al., 2020b, 2016) in terms of prediction accuracy for SRT predictions of individual listeners in complex conditions and to evaluate the effect of different individualization strategies in such conditions. FADE is an automatic speech recognition (ASR)-based model suitable to predict speech recognition and psychoacoustic experiments, both unaided and aided, using an ASR backend including a Gaussian Mixture Model and a Hidden Markov Model. It operates as an optimal detector (Jürgens and Brand, 2009), in which the same speech material and noise types are used during training and testing. This approach is particularly suitable for closed-set speech materials such as the German matrix sentence test (Schädler et al.,

2018, 2016). As signal inputs, the model operates directly on mixtures of speech and noise signals mixed at different SNRs. Logarithmically scaled Mel spectrograms are computed from these mixed signals, into which the individual hearing characteristics are incorporated. The separable Gabor filter bank features (Schädler and Kollmeier, 2015) are then extracted separately for the left and right channels and used as input to the ASR backend. From the recognition rates at different combinations of train and test SNRs, FADE determines the SRT corresponding to 50% correct speech recognition.

FADE provides two alternative binaural processing strategies. The first one applies automatic better ear listening (ABEL), and the second one uses contralateral inhibition (CAIN). The CAIN approach was used in this study. Previous work has shown comparable performance of both approaches in reverberant environments (Gerken et al., 2025a), with results in line with the established binaural speech intelligibility model BSIM (Beutelmann et al., 2010), which uses equalization-cancellation processing (Durlach, 1963). As the current study focused on the comparison across individual listeners, listener groups, and acoustic conditions, a single (i.e., CAIN) binaural approach was applied here.

2.2.1 Individualization of model parameters

The FADE model was individualized to generate listener-specific predictions by incorporating hearing loss characteristics at the feature extraction stage. Specifically, frequency- and ear-dependent individual absolute hearing thresholds were included in the logarithmically scaled Mel spectrograms to represent the attenuation component (A-component) of the Plomp model (Plomp, 1978). This was achieved by replacing signal levels below the individual hearing thresholds with the respective threshold values (Kollmeier et al., 2016; Schädler et al., 2018).

To account for suprathreshold deficits, a distortion component (D-component) was introduced as level uncertainty in the logarithmically scaled Mel spectrogram, following the concept of the Plomp model (Plomp, 1978). Three strategies for incorporating the D-component were compared in this study. As a baseline, a constant (generic) D-component of 1.9 dB was applied, representing a non-individualized suprathreshold distortion component. This value corresponds to the expected D-component for a normal-hearing listener with a PTA of 0 dB based on a linear equation proposed by Hülsmeier et al. (2022) (shown in equation (1) below) and lies within the range reported to yield optimal performance for FADE-CAIN (Schädler et al., 2020b).

In the second strategy, the same equation (1) was used to derive the D-component based on the individual PTA. The PTA was calculated separately for each ear, resulting in an ear-specific but frequency-independent D-component. Equation (1) was defined by a linear fit between the PTA and the prediction error, denoting the difference between measured and predicted SRTs (Hülsmeier et al., 2022). This linear relation describes systematic prediction errors, which can be used as estimated supra-threshold distortion components. The relation is described by

$$D=1.9dB+0.08 * PTA_{[0.5,1,2,4]kHz}, \quad (1)$$

where D is the supra-threshold distortion component, and PTA is the pure-tone average of the absolute hearing thresholds at 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz.

The third strategy was based on measured TIN detection thresholds as introduced by Schädler et al. (2020a), allowing for a frequency-dependent and ear-specific estimation of the D-component. Individual TIN thresholds were mapped to uncertainty values using inverse functions derived from FADE simulations as published by Schädler et al. (2020a). Specifically, Schädler et al. (2020a) simulated TIN detection thresholds with FADE for different values of level uncertainty at the frequencies 0.5, 1, 2, and 4 kHz. From these simulations, functions relating TIN thresholds to the D-component were obtained by fitting curves to the simulated data. These functions were subsequently inverted, such

that for a given measured TIN threshold, the corresponding level uncertainty (D-component) could be estimated. The resulting D-component values were constrained to a range between 1 dB and 20 dB.

To account for the fact that the measured TIN thresholds may be limited by audibility rather than suprathreshold processing, Schädler et al. (2020a) introduced a criterion based on the relation between individual pure-tone thresholds and normal-hearing reference TIN thresholds. This criterion indicates whether the measured TIN reflects suprathreshold processing (criterion = 0, individual tone-in-quiet threshold at least 5 dB below the normal-hearing reference TIN threshold), or is dominated by audibility limitations (criterion = 1, tone-in-quiet threshold at least 5 dB above the normal-hearing TIN reference). For intermediate cases, the criterion is linearly interpolated between 0 and 1. In the original implementation (Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3731771>), listeners with audibility-limited TIN thresholds (criterion 1), were assigned a normal-hearing reference value for the D-component. However, this procedure can lead to unrealistically low D-components for listeners with a high degree of hearing impairment, as it neglects the contribution of suprathreshold deficits in such cases. To prevent this behavior, a modified approach was introduced in the current study. Here, instead of assigning a normal-hearing D-component for listeners with criterion = 1, the PTA-based individualization of the D-component was used. For intermediate values ($0 < \text{criterion} < 1$), a weighted combination of PTA-based and TIN-based D-components was applied. This was calculated by

$$D = \text{criterion} * D_{PTA} + (1 - \text{criterion}) * D_{TIN} \quad (2)$$

where D_{PTA} is the PTA-based D-component and D_{TIN} is the TIN-based D-component.

In the original implementation of the TIN-based D-component (Schädler et al., 2020a), the PTA calculation used pure-tone thresholds measured with the SIAM procedure. In the database of this study only clinical audiograms are available. To approximate SIAM-based thresholds, the clinical audiogram thresholds were adjusted by applying a constant offset. Specifically, Schädler et al. (2020a) found that hearing thresholds measured with the SIAM procedure are on average 7.8 dB lower than those obtained from the clinical audiograms. Therefore, an offset of 7.8 dB was subtracted from the clinical audiogram hearing thresholds prior to further processing. In a further modification, values at frequencies between the two measured TIN thresholds at 500 Hz and 2000 Hz were linearly interpolated, for frequencies below 500 Hz and above 2000 Hz, the respective boundary values (500 and 2000 Hz) were used.

For six listeners, the TIN data were incomplete, i.e. TIN thresholds for single frequencies and / or ears were missing. For listeners with missing TIN thresholds for one ear, the corresponding thresholds from the contralateral ear was used. This assumption was justified by the absence of a significant ear effect on TIN thresholds ($p=0.84$, Gerken et al., 2026). For listeners with TIN thresholds available at only one frequency, the missing frequency-specific threshold was estimated based on population-level data: First, the mean difference between the TIN thresholds at 500 Hz and 2000 Hz was computed across all listeners. This mean difference was then used to extrapolate the missing TIN threshold from the available threshold.

2.2.2 Calibration of stimuli

FADE predictions were conducted with sound stimuli generated with the Room Acoustics Simulator RAZR (Ewert et al., 2025; Kirsch et al., 2023; Wendt et al., 2014), which were also used in the listener measurements and are publicly available on Zenodo: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16895975> (Gerken et al., 2025b). This stimulus set consisted of binaural noise signals for each acoustic condition, including the effect of the simulated room, as well as simulated binaural room impulse responses (BRIRs) characterizing sound propagation from the target position to the listener position. These BRIRs were convolved with OLSA sentences (Wagener et al., 1999), and reflected speech material used in the empirical measurements. Noise signals were calibrated to match the root-mean-square (RMS) levels

used in the empirical measurements (Table 1, column “RMS noise level / dB SPL”). The OLSA sentences were calibrated to a common RMS level averaged over all sentences, while preserving the small level differences introduced during test development to ensure equal intelligibility across sentences. In the measurement database (Afghah et al., 2025; Gerken et al., 2026), speech signals in complex conditions were calibrated based on the direct sound component only. In contrast, the simulated stimuli used for FADE predictions used both direct sound and reverberation for level calculation. To ensure consistency between measurements and predictions, broadband level correction offsets were applied to the measured SRTs. These offsets account for the additional energy introduced by reverberation and were determined based on the broadband signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the convolved speech and noise signals. The correction offsets were obtained from Gerken et al. (2026) and are listed in Table 1 (column “Broadband correction offset / dB”). By applying these offsets, the calibration of measured and predicted SRTs was aligned.

Table 1: Root-mean-square noise level in dB SPL and broadband correction offsets in dB for each acoustic scene.

Scene	RMS noise level / dB SPL	Broadband correction offset / dB
SON0	65	0
SON90	65	0
Living room (symmetric)	70	6.9
Living room (asymmetric)	67	5.4
Pub	74	1.6
Underground station	70	0.7

2.3 Statistical analysis

Prediction accuracy was evaluated by comparing predicted and measured SRTs using several complementary metrics. These included a) the prediction bias, defined as the mean deviation between predicted and measured SRTs, b) the root-mean-square prediction error (RMSE), quantifying the overall magnitude of prediction errors (Armstrong and Collopy, 1992), c) the coefficient of determination R^2 , computed as the squared Pearson’s correlation coefficient r and quantifying the proportion of variance explained by the model, and d) the significance level (p -value) of the correlation. R^2 values were interpreted according to Moore et al. (2013), where 0-0.3 indicates very weak, 0.3-0.5 weak, 0.5-0.7 moderate, and > 0.7 strong relationships.

For comparisons across different acoustic conditions, prediction errors, computed as the difference between the measured and predicted SRTs for each listener and condition, were statistically compared using a repeated-measures analysis of variance (ANOVA) with Greenhouse-Geisser correction. Post hoc pairwise comparisons were performed with Bonferroni correction.

To evaluate the effect of different individualization strategies, prediction performance (bias, RMSE, and R^2) was computed across listeners and acoustic conditions for each individualization strategy. Correlations between measured and predicted SRTs obtained with different individualization strategies were statistically compared using a t -statistic for dependent samples following Chen & Popovich (2002). The test statistic was defined as

$$t = (r_{13} - r_{23}) \sqrt{\frac{(N-3)(1+r_{12})}{2(1-r_{13}^2-r_{12}^2-r_{23}^2+2r_{13}^2r_{12}^2r_{23}^2)}} \quad (2)$$

where, r_{12} denotes the correlation between model versions 1 and 2, r_{13} the correlation between model version 1 and the measurements, and r_{23} the correlation between model version 2 and the measurements; N represents the sample size. The resulting t -statistic was evaluated against a t -distribution with $N-3$ degrees of freedom using the cumulative distribution function, and 2-tailed p -values were reported.

To assess systematic differences between individualization strategies at the listener level, the median prediction error across acoustic conditions was computed for each listener and model variant. These median errors were compared using a repeated-measures ANOVA with Greenhouse-Geisser correction Bonferroni-adjusted post hoc tests.

To further evaluate the relationship between measured and predicted performance beyond condition- and group-level effects, the residuals were computed by subtracting the median SRT per acoustic condition and listener group from both the measured and predicted data. These residuals of measured and predicted data were then correlated, and resulting bias, RMSE, and R^2 values were compared.

3. Results

3.1 Prediction accuracy in standard and complex conditions

The prediction accuracy of FADE was evaluated across standard audiological conditions (SON0, SON90) and complex acoustic scenes (living room symmetric and asymmetric configuration, pub, underground station). Figure 1a) shows the correlation between predicted and measured median SRTs for the model using the generic D-component. Median values were determined per listener group (NH, HI without HA, HI with HA (unaided)) and acoustic condition (6 conditions), resulting in 18 data points for both measured and predicted SRTs. Across all acoustic conditions, FADE predictions correlated moderately with the measurements on the group level ($R^2 = 0.69$). FADE systematically overestimated the speech recognition performance compared to the measured baseline, reflected in a negative bias of -6.8 dB. The overall RMSE was 7.1 dB. Despite the bias, FADE correctly predicted the expected group ordering across all conditions, with increasing median SRTs from NH listeners to HI without HA listeners and further to HI with HA (unaided) listeners.

Table 2 summarizes the bias, RMSE, squared Pearson correlation R^2 , and p -value of the correlation between measured and predicted SRTs of all listeners, separately for each acoustic condition. Measured and predicted SRTs were significantly correlated in all acoustic conditions ($p < 0.001$). However, differences were observed in absolute error metrics (bias, RMSE and R^2) across conditions. Standard conditions showed the strongest variation, with the SON0 predictions showing the smallest bias (-3.3 dB) and RMSE (4.0 dB), whereas SON90 showed the largest bias (-9.7 dB) and RMSE (10.6 dB). The complex conditions showed intermediate performance, with bias in the range of -7.1 dB to -8.6 dB and RMSE in the range of 7.5 dB to 9.0 dB. Despite these deviations, correlations remained high across complex acoustic conditions (R^2 in the range of 0.62 to 0.79).

In Figure 1b), individual prediction errors of all listeners are compared between conditions for the prediction strategy with a generic D-component. The prediction error was defined as the difference between the individual measured and predicted SRT, where negative value indicate that FADE predicts lower (better) SRTs than measured. With few exceptions in the SON0 condition, prediction errors were negative across listeners and conditions, indicating a systematic overestimation of performance. A repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a significant main effect of acoustic condition on prediction error. Mauchly's test indicated a violation of sphericity ($p < 0.001$), so Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied. The effect of acoustic condition was significant [$F(2.96, 218.89)=119.72, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2=0.62$]. Post hoc comparisons showed that prediction errors in the SON0 condition were significantly lower than in all other acoustic conditions ($p < 0.001$ for all comparisons). The prediction errors in the SON90

condition were significantly higher than in all other acoustic conditions ($p < 0.001$) except for the underground station ($p=0.051$). Only a few significant differences were found between the complex conditions: the asymmetric living room condition had significantly lower prediction errors than the underground station ($p < 0.001$), and the pub condition had significantly lower prediction errors than the symmetric living room ($p = 0.031$) and the underground station ($p < 0.001$).

Figure 1: a) Predicted and measured median SRTs in dB per listener group and acoustic condition, including bias, root-mean-square error and R^2 across the median values, and the dashed diagonal line indicating the case of a perfect prediction; b) prediction error in dB compared across the acoustic conditions, with significance of pairwise comparisons indicated by *** for $p < 0.001$, and * for $p < 0.05$. All data shown here were obtained for the predictions with generic D-component.

Table 2: Statistical measures across all listeners, separately for the different acoustic conditions. Shown are bias in dB, root-mean-square error (RMSE) in dB, squared Pearson correlation R^2 , and the p -value of the correlation. All data shown here were obtained for the predictions with generic D-component.

Condition	Bias / dB	RMSE / dB	R^2	p
SON0	-3.27	3.99	0.52	< 0.001
SON90	-9.68	10.57	0.26	< 0.001
Living room (asym)	-7.53	8.19	0.79	< 0.001
Living room (sym)	-7.84	8.49	0.62	< 0.001
Pub	-7.07	7.47	0.72	< 0.001
Underground	-8.58	9.04	0.73	< 0.001

3.2 Influence of individualization strategy

To evaluate the influence of the individualization strategy in FADE, predictions were conducted with different strategies, including a generic D-component, a PTA-based D-component, and a TIN-based D-component. Figure 2 visualizes the correlation between predicted and measured SRTs across all listeners in all acoustic conditions, separately for each individualization strategy. Across all individualization strategies, the model performance improved with an increasing degree of individualization. This trend was reflected consistently across all performance metrics. Bias decreased from -7.3 dB (generic) to -6.3 dB (PTA-based) and -5.8 dB (TIN-based), the RMSE decreased from 8.2 dB to 7.1 dB and 6.7 dB, while the correlation R^2 increased from 0.50 to 0.57 and 0.66, respectively. As

summarized in Table 3, the statistical comparison of the correlations (t -statistic for dependent samples) confirmed significant differences across all individualization strategies.

The effect of the individualization strategy at the listener level is illustrated in Figure 3, which shows the median prediction error per listener across acoustic conditions. Predictions errors tended to increase with increasing degree of hearing loss, with listeners exhibiting higher PTAs showing larger deviations between measured and predicted data. For these listeners in particular, an increased degree of individualization resulted in substantial improvements in prediction accuracy. A repeated-measures ANOVA revealed a significant main effect of individualization strategy on the median prediction error. Mauchly's test indicated a violation of sphericity ($p < 0.001$), so Greenhouse-Geisser correction was applied. There was a significant main effect of the individualization strategy [$F(1.39, 102.66)=67.64, p < 0.001, \eta_p^2=0.48$]. Post hoc comparisons (with Bonferroni corrections) showed that both the PTA-based and the TIN-based individualization resulted in significantly lower median prediction errors than the generic strategy ($p < 0.001$). In addition, the TIN-based strategy further improved the predictions in terms of the median prediction error compared to the PTA-based strategy ($p = 0.001$).

Figure 2: Correlation of predicted SRTs and measured SRTs in dB along with statistical measures in the top left corner for the FADE model versions with a) generic D-component, b) PTA-based D-component, c) TIN-based D-component. The marker color encodes the PTA of the individual listener as shown in the colorbar. The dashed diagonal line indicates the case of a perfect prediction.

Table 3: Results of the significance test to compare whether correlations of different model individualization strategies are significantly different.

compared models	t	p
generic vs. PTA-based D-component	-7.42	< 0.001
generic vs. TIN-based D-component	-5.61	< 0.001
PTA-based vs. TIN-based D-component	-3.31	< 0.001

Figure 3: Prediction error in dB comparing the model individualization strategies, shown as the median value across all 6 acoustic conditions. The values of individual listeners are plotted as markers in PTA-specific colors. Results of a Bonferroni-corrected repeated-measures ANOVA are indicated as ** for $p < 0.01$ and *** for $p < 0.001$.

To isolate the effect of the individualization strategy from listener group- and acoustic condition-specific influences, a residual analysis was performed (Figure 4). Residuals were obtained by subtracting the median SRT per listener group and acoustic condition from both predicted and measured data. The residuals were then correlated across listeners. Even after removing the listener group and acoustic condition-level effects, the beneficial effect of increased degree of model individualization remained evident. Bias decreased from -0.4 dB (generic) to -0.3 dB (PTA-based) and 0.2 dB (TIN-based), and RMSE decreased from 2.8 dB to 2.6 dB and 2.4 dB, respectively. At the same time, the correlation between predicted and measured data improved, with R^2 increasing from 0.28 to 0.36 and 0.43 for generic, PTA-based, and TIN-based strategies, respectively.

Figure 4: Correlation of residuals of predicted SRTs referenced to group- and condition-specific median in dB along with statistical measures in the top left corner for the FADE model versions with a) generic D-component, b) PTA-based D-component, c) TIN-based D-component. The marker color encodes the PTA of the individual listener as shown in the colorbar. The dashed diagonal line indicates the case of a perfect prediction.

4. Discussion

The present study evaluated the auditory model FADE for predicting speech recognition performance in hearing-impaired listeners in complex acoustic scenes, systematically comparing different strategies for listener individualization. Model predictions were compared with empirical data from a comprehensive database and evaluated in terms of bias, RMSE, R^2 , and the prediction error.

4.1 Prediction accuracy in standard and complex conditions

4.1.1 Overall model performance and comparison to literature

The present study shows that FADE can predict speech recognition for hearing-impaired listeners in complex acoustic scenes involving binaural hearing, reverberation, and realistic maskers. At the group level, predictions of median SRTs across listener groups and acoustic conditions showed moderate agreement with the measurements. At the individual level, prediction accuracy showed a systematic pattern across acoustic conditions with increased absolute deviations between predicted and measured SRTs in complex acoustic scenes compared to SON0 as reflected by higher bias and RMSE, while at the same time higher correlation between measured and predicted SRTs in complex conditions. This indicates that, although FADE exhibits systematic offsets in complex scenes, it captures the relative differences between listeners more reliably under these conditions. Considering all acoustic conditions and all listeners, a weak to moderate correlation of $R^2 = 0.5$ was found. Compared to previous studies evaluating FADE (e.g., Hülsmeyer and Kollmeier, 2022; Schädler et al., 2020a), prediction accuracy in the present work is lower. Hülsmeyer and Kollmeier (2022) reported $R^2 = 0.96$ for predictions individualized with a clinical audiogram and no D-component including listening conditions in quiet, stationary and fluctuating noise. Schädler et al. (2020a) reported $R^2 = 0.83$ for FADE predictions based on the clinical audiogram for SRTs in quiet, stationary and fluctuating noise. A key factor underlying this difference is the reduced variability in the present dataset, which focuses on speech-in-noise conditions and does not include speech-in-quiet conditions. It also represents a more homogeneous group in terms of hearing loss degree. Consequently, for literature data this spans the range of resulting SRTs much more than in the current study, making it more likely to generate a high value of R^2 . The SRTs of the dataset evaluated in the current study is more homogeneous, which naturally reduces the achievable correlation. This highlights the importance of complementary metrics such as bias and RMSE.

When comparing the present study to other auditory models, a relevant benchmark is the BSIM, including the version with blind equalization-cancellation processing (Hauth et al., 2020), which was recently evaluated for hearing-impaired listeners (Röttges et al., 2026). In that study, BSIM predictions individualized based on the pure-tone audiogram of listeners with normal hearing and with very mild to severe hearing loss resulted in $R^2 = 0.56$ for SON0 and $R^2 = 0.57$ for SON90. In the present study, FADE achieved a comparable performance in the SON0 condition ($R^2 = 0.52$), but substantially lower performance in the binaural SON90 condition ($R^2 = 0.26$). This discrepancy is notable, as FADE explicitly includes binaural processing (here: contralateral inhibition, CAIN). The results therefore suggest that, despite its binaural architecture, FADE does not yet fully capture the mechanisms underlying binaural speech recognition in spatially separated conditions. At the same time, it is important to interpret this comparison in light of methodological differences between the models. BSIM is based on an equalization-cancellation framework that explicitly models binaural unmasking, whereas FADE relies on an ASR-based feature representation with implicit binaural processing. This difference in modeling philosophy may explain why BSIM better captures binaural benefits in relatively simple spatial configurations such as SON90.

Interestingly, FADE achieved higher correlations in the complex acoustic scenes ($R^2 = 0.62$ – 0.79) than in SON90, despite larger absolute errors (higher bias and RMSE). This indicates that FADE captures relative performance differences across listeners and conditions more consistently in ecologically valid, reverberant environments than in simplified binaural test configurations. One possible explanation is that, in complex scenes, binaural advantages are reduced and dominated by other factors (e.g., reverberation, masker characteristics), which may be better reflected by the model's feature-based processing. Across all conditions, FADE systematically overestimates the speech recognition performance, i.e., it predicts too low SRTs, especially in SON90 and in complex acoustic scenes. This

tendency has also been reported in previous studies with FADE (Gerken et al., 2025a; Hülsmeyer et al., 2022; Hülsmeyer and Kollmeier, 2022; Schädler et al., 2020a). One explanation is that FADE acts as a generalized optimum detector (Holube and Kollmeier, 1996; Jürgens and Brand, 2009), using a matched training approach with highly similar stimulus statistics between training and testing. In reverberant conditions, the model has access to the same BRIR during stages (training and testing), allowing it to adapt to specific reverberation patterns. On the contrary, human listeners are exposed to a broader, less specific reverberation training that stems from a variety of different rooms and different BRIRs. This may contribute to a worse speech recognition performance in reverberant conditions for human listeners than for the auditory model and give the model an unrealistic advantage over human listeners. In future model developments, this mismatch could be addressed by modifying the training strategy to reduce its condition-specific optimization. One approach would be to expose the model during training to a broader range of reverberation conditions, rather than using exact the same BRIR for training and testing. Such variability would better approximate the diversity of acoustic environments encountered by human listeners and could prevent the model from over-adapting to a single, fixed reverberation pattern. A complementary approach would be to systematically limit the amount of reverberation-related information available to the model. For example, truncated versions of the BRIRs could be used, in which late reverberation is reduced or removed. Since late reverberation is highly diffuse and less informative for speech intelligibility, this manipulation would constrain the model's ability to exploit detailed reverberation cues that may not be perceptually accessible to listeners. In this way, the model would rely more strongly on robust speech features rather than on condition-specific reverberation characteristics.

Further limitations may arise from modeling of suprathreshold deficits that are not captured by the audiogram, often discussed in the context of "hidden hearing loss". Lavandier et al. (2021) reported a systematic overestimation of speech intelligibility in predictions for normal-hearing listeners, where model predictions tended to represent the best-performing listeners well but failed to account for individuals' higher SRTs. The authors attributed this limitation to incomplete modeling of suprathreshold processing deficits, suggesting that factors beyond audibility, such as internal noise, temporal processing limitations, or even cognitive contributions may play a role in speech-in-noise performance. This aligns with the present findings, where audiogram-based individualization alone was insufficient to fully capture inter-individual variability. One approach to address this limitation in the current study was to incorporate additional listener-specific information through tone-in-noise detection thresholds, as discussed in section 4.2. These measures provide a behavioral estimate of auditory processing in challenging listening conditions. While this does not fully resolve the issue of unmodeled cognitive or supra-auditory effects, it represents a step toward reducing systematic prediction bias by enriching the model with information beyond the audiogram.

Another potential source of systematic deviations between predicted and measured SRTs may be a residual mismatch between the simulated acoustic signals used for model predictions and the actual acoustic conditions at the listener's ear during the experiments. Although the listening laboratory was a calibrated and acoustically treated room, it was not fully anechoic. Consequently, the acoustic signals reaching the listeners includes room-related contributions from the playback room that are not explicitly represented in the simulated signals processed by the model. Such discrepancies are likely to be multifactorial and may be particularly pronounced in acoustically complex conditions, where small differences in the representation of spatial cues, early reflections, or signal mixing assumptions can differentially affect model and listener outcomes. This is especially relevant given that the measured binaural benefit in SON90 was comparatively small in the present dataset, suggesting a possible compression of spatial release effects in human performance that is not fully captured by the model. In a follow-up study, this effect could be investigated and quantified by conducting FADE predictions with recorded noise and BRIR signals from the playback room, which are available for the present

dataset (Gerken et al., 2025b). However, this was beyond the scope of the current evaluation study, which focused on comparing individualization strategies under a controlled and fully simulation-based modeling framework.

4.1.2 Model sensitivity to spatial and reverberant scene properties

To compare the influence of spatial configuration independent of reverberation effects, the prediction performance in SONO and SON90 can be directly contrasted. Importantly, the binaural benefit (difference between SONO and SON90) is overestimated by FADE compared to the measured data. This indicates that the model exploits interaural differences more strongly than listeners in the present dataset. For future model developments, these findings indicate a need to refine the interplay between the hearing loss and its implementation in the model and the binaural processing stage, as the current configuration appears to overemphasize interaural cues. This finding is consistent with Gerken et al. (2025a), who compared two different binaural versions of FADE, i.e., FADE CAIN and FADE ABEL. FADE ABEL applies purely automatic better ear listening without additional binaural processing as in FADE CAIN, where additionally, the difference vector between the left and right ear was used in terms of contralateral inhibition. They showed, that in anechoic conditions, FADE ABEL resulted in notably higher SRTs than FADE CAIN, but this difference vanished in reverberant conditions. Therefore, in realistic, i.e. reverberant conditions, binaural processing advantages are strongly reduced. Therefore, it is expected that FADE ABEL and CAIN would lead to comparable results in complex scenes as used in this study. Furthermore, the binaural benefit varies substantially between listeners, so while some listeners experience a high benefit in spatially separated conditions, other listeners might experience little to no benefit (Gallun, 2021). The current FADE model does not include any individual information about spatial hearing abilities, such as binaural unmasking efficiency or cognitive contributions. Previous studies reported that models which are successful in predicting binaural performance use further metrics like cognitive function measures (Gallun and Jakien, 2019), speech intelligibility and age (Kubiak et al., 2020).

Differences in speech recognition prediction performance between complex acoustic scenes, e.g. comparing the pub and the underground station further suggest that multiple interacting factors influence prediction accuracy, including reverberation, the architecture of the environment, or the type and spatial configuration of the noise sources. However, these factors cannot be disentangled with the current dataset. A systematical variation of individual acoustic parameters within controlled scenes would be required, as demonstrated in Gerken et al. (2025a) for normal-hearing listeners.

[4.2 Influence of individualization strategy](#)

4.2.1 Advantages and limitations of individualization strategies

FADE predictions of speech recognition performance were analyzed using three different listener individualization strategies. It was shown that an increased degree of individualization is beneficial for the prediction performance, reflected by a significant decrease in prediction error and by a significant improvement in correlations of the three model versions with the measured data. The generic D-component of 1.9 dB can be interpreted as a representative estimation of suprathreshold distortion effects of normal-hearing listeners, as the value also emerges from the assumption of 0 dB HL hearing thresholds for the linear estimation by Hülsmeyer et al. (2022). While this fixed parameter provides a robust baseline, it cannot account for listener-specific supra-auditory distortions, which become increasingly relevant in hearing-impaired populations. The PTA-based strategy extends the model; however, it still represents a frequency-independent suprathreshold correction and does not differentiate suprathreshold deficits in listeners with comparable PTA. This explains why improvements are most pronounced in listeners with higher PTA values, while residual prediction errors remain substantial. In contrast, the TIN-based individualization incorporates behavioral measures of auditory performance

in noise and therefore provides a more direct and frequency-specific estimate of suprathreshold deficits. This additional information leads to the most consistent improvement across listeners and conditions.

A key limitation of the TIN-based strategy lies in its dependence on the measurement context of tone-in-noise detection thresholds. If such thresholds are obtained close to audibility limits, they may not fully reflect suprathreshold processing capabilities, thereby reducing their interpretability as a distortion metric. Both the present study and Schädler et al. (2020a) addressed this issue by applying different handling strategies for listeners with elevated thresholds, as described in the Methods section. In future studies, it would be reasonable to individualize the level of the masking noise for the TIN measurements and ensure that the experiment is done in suprathreshold conditions.

From the practical perspective, the three strategies represent a trade-off between measurement effort and predictive accuracy. The generic and PTA-based strategies are readily applicable in clinical settings, as they require only standard audiometric data. The TIN-based predictions, while more accurate, require additional psychoacoustic testing and are therefore demanding in terms of time and experimental resources. Therefore, the PTA-based individualization strategy may represent a pragmatic compromise for routine applications, whereas TIN-based strategy is preferable when higher prediction accuracy is required.

4.2.2 Individual deviations and listener-specific effects

The individual speech recognition predictions in standard and complex acoustic scenes revealed substantial inter-listener variability that was not fully captured by any of the tested individualization strategies. This was reflected in the broad spread of prediction errors throughout all individualization strategies and acoustic conditions. The effect of the individualization strategy on the prediction accuracy also differed between listeners and was most pronounced for the listeners with the highest PTA values. These listeners have the strongest differences between generic and PTA-based D-component values. This is expected, as PTA-based corrections scale directly with hearing loss. For NH listeners PTA-based corrections converge towards the generic value of 1.9 dB, limiting the potential for improvement. For the TIN-based strategy, inter-individual variability becomes more complex, as the D-component is derived from suprathreshold measurements (tone-in-noise detection), which can vary substantially even between listeners with similar audiograms (Hawley et al., 2017; Oetting et al., 2016; Pienkowski, 2017).

An additional source of variability likely arises from day-to-day variability within the same listener (Kuhlmann et al., 2023), which is not captured in the underlying dataset, as it does not include a test-retest measurement. This intra-individual performance depending on the date of the measurement is currently not reflected in the model predictions and therefore poses another source of deviations between predicted and measured SRTs.

4.2.3 Comparison with literature

The observed improvements due to listener individualization are consistent with previous findings of FADE and related auditory models. Hülsmeyer and Kollmeier (2022) reported systematic improvements in prediction accuracy of FADE for monaural and less complex stimuli when increasing the level of audiometric detail, showing a reduction in RMSE from 6.3 dB (no D-component) to 5.6 dB (PTA-based D component) and 5.1 dB (TIN-based D-component), with the strongest performance obtained using a high-resolution sweep audiogram (RMSE between 3.3 dB and 4.3 dB). The current evaluation extends these findings to binaural and complex acoustic scenes, where a similar pattern of improvement with increasing individualization was observed. Importantly, this comparison suggests that the benefit of

suprathreshold individualization is robust across stimulus complexity, but does not eliminate systematic limitations in more realistic environments. The absence of a sweep audiogram in the present dataset likely reduced the achievable upper bound of prediction accuracy, consistent with the conclusions of Hülsmeyer and Kollmeier (2022), who highlighted the value of high-resolution audiometric input for model precision.

The relevance of explicit suprathreshold modeling has also been demonstrated in other auditory modeling frameworks. For example, Röttges et al. (2026) showed that introducing a listener-specific suprathreshold component in the BSIM framework significantly improved prediction accuracy in SON0 and SON90, independent of the specific implementation strategy. Similar benefits have been reported in related models incorporating internal noise or distortion-like mechanisms (Lavandier et al., 2021; Vicente et al., 2021, 2020), supporting the general notion that audiogram-based information alone is insufficient to capture suprathreshold auditory limitations in speech-in-noise perception.

Overall, the present findings indicate that incorporating listener-specific suprathreshold information substantially improves model predictions. Future work should therefore focus on extending these individualization strategies toward aided listening conditions and on improving the robustness of the model in reverberant and spatially complex scenes.

5. Conclusions

The present study evaluated the accuracy of the auditory model FADE for predicting SRTs in both standard audiological conditions and complex acoustic scenes. Overall, the model showed a moderate correlation across all acoustic conditions on the group level, demonstrating its capability to capture systematic differences across listener groups and acoustic scenes, including multiple spatially separated maskers and speech-on-speech masking. This establishes an openly available benchmark for model-based audiology in complex acoustic scenes, using the FADE model as an example, based on a comprehensive set of empirical reference data.

A central contribution of this work is the systematic comparison of different individualization strategies in binaural and acoustically complex conditions. Increasing the degree of individualization significantly improved prediction performance, with the incorporation of tone-in-noise detection thresholds providing the most accurate results. This highlights the importance of suprathreshold auditory processing for individualized model-based audiology, beyond what can be captured by audiometric thresholds alone.

Although systematic deviations between predicted and measured SRTs remain, particularly at the individual level, the model reliably captures relative performance differences across listeners and conditions. This presents a major step towards model-based audiology in complex acoustic scenes. Besides the model's limitations in terms of absolute SRT predictions, FADE is capable of predicting individual hearing performance for a range of audiological conditions given just a few individual input parameters (i.e., the audiogram and, optionally, TIN detection thresholds). This supports its applicability for comparative analyses and for investigating the effects of acoustic scene characteristics and listener-specific factors.

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Declaration of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The empirical dataset used as reference data in this article is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14864856>, published along with the article Afghah et al. (2025).

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used DeepL Write in order to improve the wording of the manuscript. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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